

<https://miyelin.com/sma-file-1-what-is-sma/>

Diagnosis and Treatment Methods

We've talked about SMA5q before, and it focuses on many more variables in diagnosis and treatment. In the article published in Cell in 1995, chromosome 5q13, which is linked to the SMA gene, was paired. According to this article, homozygous deletion of the SMN1 gene on 5q13 was defined as the diagnosis of SMA [1].

The SMN protein, a polypeptide consisting of 294 amino acids, is found in the nucleus and cytoplasm [2]. In an experiment on SMN gene on 5q13, a candidate gene for human spinal muscular atrophy, abolition of SMN function in mice proved fatal, causing the mice to die in the uterus. [3].

Individuals with SMA, the second most common autosomal recessive disorder, have homozygous loss of function of the motor neuron gene SMN1 at 5q13, but retains the regulatory SMN2 gene. Currently, the most common diagnosis is the detection of homozygous deletion of SMN1 Exon 7 (SMN Δ 7) [4]. There are ready-made kits available today to display these deletions.

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Figure 1 RT-PCR analysis of endogenous SMN transcripts from EBV-transformed lymphocytes of SMA and control individuals [5].[/caption]

Symptoms of SMA

SMA symptoms were identified with SMA types categorically. In our previous series of articles, we talked about different types of SMA. SMA is clinically examined in 4 different types. SMA type 0 occurs before birth.

The general symptoms of SMA are as follows

- Eating and swallowing problems
- Decreased or strained reflexes
- Inability to maintain head control

SMA is diagnosed by genetic testing or by performing a muscle biopsy.

Type I.

Type 1 SMA or Werdnig-Hoffmann; Less than 10% of SMA Type 1 patients have only one copy of the SMN2 gene, and it usually has a fatal course. Multiple cases of congenital heart defects have been reported in patients with genetically confirmed SMA. Despite these findings, there are few proven cases of cardiac rhythm abnormalities in SMA Type 1 cases. In addition, a series of studies conducted in 2005 revealed irregular skin responses to blood pressure fluctuations and temperature changes [6].

Type II.

Type 2 SMA or Subowitz Syndrome; Patients can usually sit, but hypotonia is seen. While progressive scoliosis causes restrictive lung disease in the eyebrows, tremors may occur in the hands. Most of the deaths are due to respiratory distress. 70% of patients survive to age 25 [7].

Type III.

Type 3 SMA or Kugelberg-Welander disease; Although patients are generally known to be standing, they may need a wheelchair in the future. They also often do not experience lung disease and this does not affect their survival rate [7].

Type IV.,

Type 4 SMA or Adult SMA; Patients are older than 21 years and it is the mildest type of SMA. Patients can stand, only with mild leg weakness, they can apply to the doctor. It does not affect life expectancy [7].

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